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Title: SOP to turn On and Off the Orbitrap Exploris 480 and Vanquish Duo liquid chromatograph.

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Make a note about the LC-MS turn On/Off and baking the Orbitrap Chamber to the Logbook.

SW: Xcalibur 4.7.69.37, Thermo Scientific for SII Xcalibur 1.7.0.468, Orbitrap Exploris Tune 4.3.458.15

To turn Off Orbitrap Exploris 480 and Vanquish Duo LC

1. In Orbitrap Exploris Tune Application (Tune window), place the MS to Off Mode (Figure 1).

All high voltages are shut off as well as the sheath and auxiliary gas.

Figure 1. Power mode icons showing the selected mode

1. Close all the programs on the screen.
2. For the MS, place the Main Power switch to Off Mode while Electronics service remain at the Operating Mode (**Figure 2**).

← **Figure 2.** The power entry module is located on the right side of Orbitrap Exploris 480

No. 1: Holders for power supplies of syringe pump and the switching valve

No. 2: Main supply connector

No. 3: Power supply for syringe pump and switching valves

No. 4: **Main Power** switch, with **ON** for the upper position and **OFF** for the lower position

No. 5: **Electronics service** switch, with **Operating Mode** for the upper position and **Service Only** for the lower position

3. Optionally, by using the on/off valve above the MS, close the supply line for Nitrogen ECD 5.5.
4. Turn Off Vanquish Duo by the system power button (on the front left side of the Vanquish system base). Optionally, turn Off each the LC module by its main power switch.
5. Turn Off the divert valve by the socket unplugging.
6. Turn Off the PC.

To turn On Orbitrap Exploris 480 and Vanquish Duo LC

1. Turn On the PC, sign in by the Thermo account and wait till the PC connects to the local network.
An indication appears on the right side of the bottom screen banner.
2. By clicking the *Orbitrap Exploris Tune Application* icon, open Tune window to start monitoring the MS.
For Chromeleon 7.3.1: click the *Chromeleon* icon to open Chromeleon Console, there go to Instrument section to check Orbitrap Exploris Tune Application.
3. If closed, open the on/off valve of the supply line for Nitrogen ECD 5.5 and check the output pressure of **6.0 bar for Nitrogen ECD 5.5** remain unaffected.
4. For the MS, place the Main Power switch to On Mode to run forepumps and turbomolecular pumps.
 - a) *Once the turbomolecular pump exceeds 90 % of its rotation speed within 15 mins, the MS will try to start automatic bake-out with 10 hours of heating and 3 hours of cooling.*
 - b) *By initiating the cooling stage, the vacuum of the Orbitrap analyzer is going to be monitored.*
 - c) *Following the cooling, the front panel LED becomes green once all the tune application LEDs are green and the Orbitrap analyzer temperature is below 45°C.*
 - d) *Once the vacuum of the Orbitrap analyzer is below 1E-8 mbar, the power supply of high voltage electronics and the tube heater is switched On.*
5. Turn On the Vanquish Duo LC by the system power button. Optionally, turn on each LC module by its main power switch.
6. Turn On the divert valve while it displays 1 or 2 indicating to the MS or waste position.
7. By clicking the *blue X* icon, open Xcalibur and go to Instrument Setup. At Thermo Xcalibur Instrument Setup window, open SII Xcalibur and check Direct Control to monitor the LC.
For Chromeleon 7.3.1: in Chromeleon Console open Instrument section, there go to LC bookmark to monitor the LC modules.
8. After the 4d point has successfully passed, check the **threshold pressure limits < 3.5 mbar** and **< 1E-8 mbar** for the **Fore Vacuum** and the **Ultra High Vacuum**, respectively.
9. Afterwards, place the MS to Standby mode (the temperature of ion transfer tube increases) and then let the MS stabilize.

Note: The used figures were obtained from Orbitrap Exploris Series (Thermo Fisher Scientific): Operating Manual